

Supplementary Note 1.

Univariate and or multivariate GWAS summary statistics are not sufficient to reveal the mechanisms that underlie pathogenesis. Rather, it is the downstream analysis of these genetic datasets that reveal how complex traits may develop at the biochemical level. Using summary statistics as input, a majority of gene-based tests assign variants based on reference genome gene position, often including SNPs within pre-specified upstream and downstream windows to capture potential regulatory elements. However, such methodologies are not capable of evaluating cell type-specific gene associations. Nuclear organization is highly cell type-dependent and is extremely correlated to the differences in transcription across cell types (Takei et al. 2021). There is significant variation in nuclear volume, chromatin scaling, chromosome territory size, overall 3D chromatin structures of inactive and active chromatin, radial positioning and consequent differences in transcriptional activity across cell types, even across neuronal subclasses. (Lui et al. 2015). There is variation amongst the group(s) of SNPs that affect any given gene's expression across cell types. Due to this immense limitation, there is a lack of cell type-specific gene-based interpretation of GWAS. To date, H-MAGMA is the only gene-analysis framework that helps overcome cell type-dependent nuclear organization limitations by leveraging chromatin interactions to map noncoding variants to genes. However, open-sourced Hi-C datasets are extremely sparse, attenuating our ability to view genetic risk through a "cell-specific" lens. Nonetheless, by mapping risk genes in neurotransmitter-specific neurons from the genetic data of psychiatric disorders driven by aberrant neurotransmission, one inherently targets genes that are core to the cell type's signaling machinery (Woodward et al. 2025). Quantifying risk genes for specific cell types will add specificity and depth to research, likely expediting the unraveling of complex trait pathogenesis.

Supplementary Note 2. Disregarding the cell adhesion aspect of *PTPRD*

We first investigated the role of *PTPRD*'s cell adhesion mediating fibronectin III and Ig domains, as the receptor is highly implicated in synaptic formation and differentiation (Cortés et al. 2024). However, combined knockout of 3 receptor type protein tyrosine phosphatases, *PTPRD*, *PTPRS*, and *PTPRF* yielded intact synapse structure and function in cultured hippocampal neurons (Emperador-Melero, de Nola, & Kaeser, 2021). In another study, *PTPRD* KO mice exhibited normal excitatory and inhibitory synaptic functions (Ah Han et al. 2020). The literature suggests that *PTPRD* mediated cell adhesion contributes redundantly to the overall anatomy of the neuronal synapse, thus we decided not to pursue the topic further in our biological annotation.

Supplementary Note 3. *PTPRD/TrkB* and *PDGFRB*

Substrate-trapping pulldowns with *PTPRD*'s D1 phosphatase domain have supported direct dephosphorylation interactions with the receptor protein kinases, platelet derived growth factor beta (*PDGFRB*) and tropomyosin receptor type beta (*TrkB* encoded by the *NTRK2* gene) in mice. These findings are consistent with recent literature, naming *PDGFRB* and *TrkB* as substrates of *PTPRD* (Uhl & Martinez, 2019) (Xu et al. 2022). In the absence of *PTPRD*, *TrkB* and *PDGFRB*, which potentiate downstream the *MEK-ERK* pathway, remain hyperactivated. Higher concentrations of downstream effectors, *MEK* and *ERK*, are observed in *PTPRD* KO/HET mice when compared to the WT (Toita et al. 2020). In light of these developments, we explored the intricacies of the two *PTPRD* substrates, *TrkB* and *PDGFRB*, and the potential of their downstream effectors to hold functional relevance in dopamine neurons.

Supplementary Note 4. Disregarding *PDGFRB*

The single-cell, dopamine neuron RNA expression dataset curated by Kamath et al. 2022 was used as a helping guide for the pathway analysis of *PTPRD*, allowing us to rule out any candidates that are expressed in negligible amounts in human dopamine neurons (Kamath et al. 2022). Given the negligible expression of *PDGFRB* in dopamine neurons (Supplementary Fig 3), the gene was excluded from analysis as a downstream effector of *PTPRD* signaling. Supplementary Figs 1-2 display the mean RNA expression (Unique molecular identifiers) for *PTPRD* and *NTRK2* for 10 subclasses of clustered dopamine neurons. Both genes appear to be highly expressed across dopamine neuron subclasses, thus *NTRK2* was subjected to further analysis in the context of a downstream effector of *PTPRD*.

Expression summary for gene: NTRK2

Cell_Type	Mean	N Cells
CALB1_CALCR	21.76	2479
CALB1_CRYM_CCDC68	16.98	931
CALB1_GEM	25.06	884
CALB1_PPP1R17	9.70	1358
CALB1_RBP4	12.45	763
CALB1_TRHR	14.60	486
Other	4.96	412292
SOX6_AGTR1	18.20	8498
SOX6_DDT	11.67	2414
SOX6_GFRA2	17.75	1589
SOX6_PART1	16.31	2646

Supplementary Fig 1. RNA expression tables displaying mean UMIs in 10 subclasses of human

dopamine neuron clusters from the Kamath et. al 2022 dataset.

Expression summary for gene: PTPRD

Cell_Type	Mean	N Cells
CALB1_CALCR	18.94	2479
CALB1_CRYM_CCDC68	16.20	931
CALB1_GEM	57.89	884
CALB1_PPP1R17	18.19	1358
CALB1_RBP4	25.36	763
CALB1_TRHR	44.55	486
Other	23.46	412292
SOX6_AGTR1	19.40	8498
SOX6_DDT	11.59	2414
SOX6_GFRA2	16.69	1589
SOX6_PART1	13.33	2646

Supplementary Fig 2. RNA expression tables displaying mean UMIs in 10 subclasses of human dopamine neuron clusters from the Kamath et. al 2022 dataset.

Expression summary for gene: PDGFRB

Cell_Type	Mean	N Cells
CALB1_CALCR	0.03	2479
CALB1_CRYM_CCDC68	0.02	931
CALB1_GEM	0.06	884
CALB1_PPP1R17	0.02	1358
CALB1_RBP4	0.02	763
CALB1_TRHR	0.03	486
Other	0.26	412292
SOX6_AGTR1	0.02	8498
SOX6_DDT	0.03	2414
SOX6_GFRA2	0.03	1589
SOX6_PART1	0.02	2646

Supplementary Fig 3. RNA expression tables displaying mean UMIs in 10 subclasses of human dopamine neuron clusters from the Kamath et. al 2022 dataset.

Supplementary Note 5. *ERK1/2* signaling involved in regulation *KCNQ2* K⁺ ion channels

Given the propensity of *PTPRD* inhibition to increase *MEK/ERK* signaling, we reviewed neuron associated *ERK1/2* literature to gain insights into pathways that may hold functional relevance in DA neurons. *ERK1/2* is heavily implicated in the LTP of neurons in the nucleus accumbens in response to dopaminergic signaling (Nagia et al. 2016). Dopamine-mediated signaling of the D1 receptor activates the *PKA/RAP1/ERK* cascade in medium spiny neurons of the nucleus accumbens to regulate membrane excitability (Nagia et al. 2016). In HEK293 cells *in vivo*, *ERK* inhibits KCNQ-mediated K⁺ current via direct phosphorylation of *KCNQ2* ion channels at Ser414 and Ser476. Additionally, D1 receptor agonist induced inhibition of the KCNQ-mediated currents were attenuated by *ERK* inhibition and conditional deletion of *KCNQ2* in medium spiny neurons (Tsuboi et al. 2022). Elevated *ERK1/2* signaling in the absence of *PTPRD* may alter the ability of DA neurons to maintain excitability homeostasis via *DIR/ERK/KCNQ2* signaling.

Expression summary for gene: *KCNQ2*

Cell_Type	Mean	N Cells
CALB1_CALCR	1.84	2479
CALB1_CRYM_CCDC68	1.32	931
CALB1_GEM	1.59	884
CALB1_PPP1R17	1.01	1358
CALB1_RBP4	1.03	763
CALB1_TRHR	1.61	486
Other	0.43	412292
SOX6_AGTR1	1.40	8498
SOX6_DDT	0.99	2414
SOX6_GFRA2	1.41	1589
SOX6_PART1	1.25	2646

Supplementary Fig 4. RNA expression tables displaying mean UMIs in 10 subclasses of human dopamine neuron clusters from the Kamath et. al 2022 dataset.

Supplementary Note 6. *BDNF/NTRK2*'s role in regulating survival and neuroplasticity

TrkB is implicated in the survival and neuroplasticity of dopamine neurons, specifically as the high affinity, canonical receptor for the neurotrophic factor, brain-derived neurotrophic factor (*BDNF*) (Hydman et al. 1991). A single injection of *BDNF* into the ventral tegmental area of rats elicits sustained increase in cocaine-seeking behavior lasting up to 30 days, an effect that is negated by the *MEK* inhibitor U0126 (Lu et al. 2004). *BDNF* is a promoter of DA neuron survival and axonal growth, regulating survival and neuroplasticity of DA neurons (Østergaard et al. 1996).

Supplementary Note 7. *NTRK2/VAV2* and LTP

Immunoprecipitations with anti-phosphotyrosine antibodies and flag-tagged *TrkB* have supported direct phosphorylation interactions between *VAV2* and *TrkB* in mouse hippocampal neurons. *VAV2* is a guanine exchange factor for the rho family of GTPases, which regulate the actin cytoskeleton, playing an essential role in dendritic spine formation, motility, and morphology (Lui et al. 2000). Upon *BDNF* stimulation, reduced increase of *Rac1*-GTP concentrations is observed in *VAV2/3* *-/-* mice when compared to the wild type, suggesting that *VAV2*'s GEF domain is required for *Rac1*-GTP synthesis. In assays of *BDNF* induced dendritic spine head growth, no significant changes in spine head area were observed in the *VAV2/3* *-/-* mice, while the WT exhibited significant increases in spine head area. Additionally, post administration of theta-burst stimulation at CA1 glutamatergic synapses, significantly reduced long term potentiation was observed in *VAV2/3* deficient mice when compared to wildtype (Hale et al. 2011). Is it likely that this *VAV2/3* mechanism is a critical component of *Rac1*-GDP's

transition into *Rac1*-GTP in the context of dendritic spine head growth and actin cytoskeleton regulation, which is essential for regulating LTP. In the absence of *PTPRD*, hyperactivation of *TrkB/VAV2* signaling may result in excessive dendritic spine head growth, leading to chronic excitability of DA neurons.

Expression summary for gene: VAV2

Cell_Type	Mean	N Cells
CALB1_CALCR	5.07	2479
CALB1_CRYM_CCDC68	2.76	931
CALB1_GEM	4.74	884
CALB1_PPP1R17	1.76	1358
CALB1_RBP4	2.13	763
CALB1_TRHR	3.70	486
Other	0.34	412292
SOX6_AGTR1	4.89	8498
SOX6_DDT	3.01	2414
SOX6_GFRA2	3.14	1589
SOX6_PART1	3.26	2646

Supplementary Fig 4. RNA expression tables displaying mean UMIs in 10 subclasses of human dopamine neuron clusters from the Kamath et. al 2022 dataset.

Expression summary for gene: RAC1

Cell_Type	Mean	N Cells
CALB1_CALCR	2.10	2479
CALB1_CRYM_CCDC68	2.23	931
CALB1_GEM	2.18	884
CALB1_PPP1R17	1.67	1358
CALB1_RBP4	5.82	763
CALB1_TRHR	2.28	486
Other	1.45	412292
SOX6_AGTR1	1.75	8498
SOX6_DDT	4.37	2414
SOX6_GFRA2	2.06	1589
SOX6_PART1	2.00	2646

Supplementary Fig 5. RNA expression tables displaying mean UMIs in 10 subclasses of human dopamine neuron clusters from the Kamath et. al 2022 dataset.

Supplementary Note 8. *BDNF/TrkB* signaling and LTP in DA neurons from glutamatergic synapse input

Dopamine neurons require *BDNF* to undergo LTP from glutamatergic excitatory synapse input. When presynaptic stimuli of excitatory glutamatergic afferents are applied to dopamine neurons, the production of sustained excitatory postsynaptic potential (EPSP), is only observed when dopamine neurons are pretreated with exogenous *BDNF* in vivo (Pu et al. 2006). *BDNF* induced actin cytoskeleton regulation and consequent dendritic spine head growth likely contributes to the observed requirement of *BDNF* for the LTP of DA neurons in response to glutamatergic input across studies.

Supplementary Note 9. DA neuron *BDNF/TrkB* signaling and inhibitory LDP of the GABAergic synapse

BDNF signaling in DA neurons is also implicated in inhibitory long term depression (I-LTD) (Zhong et al. 2015). Zhong et al. 2015, suggest that *BDNF* acts via *TrkB* to activate phospholipase C and diacylglycerol lipase to cleave phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate for the synthesis of 2-arachidonoylglycerol (2-AG), in response to otherwise subthreshold GABAergic afferent stimulation (10 Hz, 5 min). The 2-AG is then released in retrograde fashion by the DA neurons to engage presynaptic cannabinoid receptor type 1 (CB₁) receptors of the GABAergic ISPCs, producing long-term depression of GABAergic IPSC input towards DA neurons. DA-neuron *BDNF* knockout abolishes this eCB-mediated I-LTD, and both bath or systemic application of the *TrkB* agonist *DHF* fully restores it. In further support of this pathway, *BDNF* released onto ventral tegmental area dopamine neurons induced inhibitory LDP (Zhong et al. 2015). It is likely that *TrkB* signaling in dopamine neurons is required to potentiate inhibitory LTP upon stimulation from GABAergic synaptic currents. The absence of *PTPRD* may result in excessive retrograde inhibition of GABAergic synapses via hyperactivated *TrkB* signaling, contributing to the chronic excitation of DA neurons.

Supplementary Note 10. *PTPRD* deficient mice experience enhanced long-term potentiation

A common trend we have identified from the potential downstream effectors of *PTPRD* is chronic excitability. These findings are consistent with *PTPRD* KO/Inhibition literature that assay neuronal excitability, of which there is a singular publication. Uetani et al. 2000, generated *PTPRD*-deficient mice and found that, despite normal hippocampal histology, these animals exhibited severe growth retardation and semi-lethality due to impaired food intake (Uetani et al. 2000). Although confirmatory research would be required, the absence of *PTPRD*'s D1 phosphatase activity in DA neuron-mediated reward circuitry may have contributed to decreased food intake. Behavioral assays revealed that *PTPRD*-deficient mice had significant deficits in

spatial learning and working memory. Long-term potentiation at both CA1 and CA3 synapses was significantly augmented in *PTPRD*-deficient mice. These findings imply *PTPRD* as a critical regulator of hippocampal synaptic neuroplasticity and underscore that optimal, not maximal, LTP is required for normal memory formation (Uetani et al. 2000). With the lack of research surrounding *PTPRD* assays in DA neurons, we are left to extrapolate from research of other neurotransmitter specific neurons. As the current literature suggests, core pathways like *TrkB/BDNF* and *MEK/ERK* are typically conserved across neurons (Gupta et al., 2013) (Hirata et al., 2017). It is biologically plausible that *PTPRD* may play non-redundant roles in DA neuron LTP, from which strict homeostatic control is required to achieve optimal reward processing.

Supplementary Note 11. Sustained excitability and its effects on metaplasticity

When neurons are chronically excited, the signal threshold for inducing LTP increases, a phenomenon known as metaplasticity. The chronic excitation of hippocampal CA1 neurons triggers homeostatic adaptations that raise the threshold for structural LTP (sLTP) (Ueda et al. 2000). After 24 hours of bicuculline treatment, a GABA receptor antagonist, NMDAR-mediated Ca^{2+} influx was downregulated and Calcium/calmodulin-dependent protein kinase II (*CaMKII*) was inhibited, a protein that plays essential roles in driving dendritic spine growth. As a result, the same glutamate uncaging or photoactivatable *CaMKII* activation that normally induces sLTP in controls fails entirely unless much stronger stimulation is administered. (Ueda et al. 2000). Chronic overexcitation of neurons moves the LTP signal threshold upward, preventing hyperactive circuits. The phenomenon of metaplasticity may underlie *PTPRD*-deficient mice's altered behavioral responses to cocaine administration, especially the reduction in break points and lever presses. The absence of *PTPRD* and hyperactivation of *TrkB* signaling may result in

chronic excitation, increasing LTP signal threshold and attenuating cocaine's ability to induce LTP in dopamine neurons and reinforce reward-related behavior.

Expression summary for gene: CAMK2A

Cell_Type	Mean	N Cells
CALB1_CALCR	1.62	2479
CALB1_CRYM_CCDC68	1.97	931
CALB1_GEM	0.95	884
CALB1_PPP1R17	1.13	1358
CALB1_RBP4	1.26	763
CALB1_TRHR	1.38	486
Other	0.53	412292
SOX6_AGTR1	1.00	8498
SOX6_DDT	0.84	2414
SOX6_GFRA2	1.15	1589
SOX6_PART1	1.60	2646

Supplementary Fig 6. RNA expression tables displaying mean UMIs in 10 subclasses of human dopamine neuron clusters from the Kamath et. al 2022 dataset.

Expression summary for gene: CAMK2B

Cell_Type	Mean	N Cells
CALB1_CALCR	7.56	2479
CALB1_CRYM_CCDC68	5.96	931
CALB1_GEM	7.38	884
CALB1_PPP1R17	4.50	1358
CALB1_RBP4	6.57	763
CALB1_TRHR	6.63	486
Other	1.94	412292
SOX6_AGTR1	7.23	8498
SOX6_DDT	6.90	2414
SOX6_GFRA2	6.00	1589
SOX6_PART1	6.18	2646

Supplementary Fig 7. RNA expression tables displaying mean UMIs in 10 subclasses of human dopamine neuron clusters from the Kamath et. al 2022 dataset.

Expression summary for gene: CAMK2B

Cell_Type	Mean	N Cells
CALB1_CALCR	7.56	2479
CALB1_CRYM_CCDC68	5.96	931
CALB1_GEM	7.38	884
CALB1_PPP1R17	4.50	1358
CALB1_RBP4	6.57	763
CALB1_TRHR	6.63	486
Other	1.94	412292
SOX6_AGTR1	7.23	8498
SOX6_DDT	6.90	2414
SOX6_GFRA2	6.00	1589
SOX6_PART1	6.18	2646

Supplementary Fig 8. RNA expression tables displaying mean UMIs in 10 subclasses of human dopamine neuron clusters from the Kamath et. al 2022 dataset.

Expression summary for gene: CAMK2D

Cell_Type	Mean	N Cells
CALB1_CALCR	14.81	2479
CALB1_CRYM_CCDC68	12.74	931
CALB1_GEM	14.68	884
CALB1_PPP1R17	7.64	1358
CALB1_RBP4	9.44	763
CALB1_TRHR	12.27	486
Other	3.45	412292
SOX6_AGTR1	20.72	8498
SOX6_DDT	13.31	2414
SOX6_GFRA2	13.27	1589
SOX6_PART1	14.19	2646

Supplementary Fig 9. RNA expression tables displaying mean UMIs in 10 subclasses of human dopamine neuron clusters from the Kamath et. al 2022 dataset.

Expression summary for gene: CAMK2G

Cell_Type	Mean	N Cells
CALB1_CALCR	6.08	2479
CALB1_CRYM_CCDC68	4.92	931
CALB1_GEM	5.46	884
CALB1_PPP1R17	3.18	1358
CALB1_RBP4	4.56	763
CALB1_TRHR	4.95	486
Other	1.77	412292
SOX6_AGTR1	6.41	8498
SOX6_DDT	5.14	2414
SOX6_GFRA2	4.91	1589
SOX6_PART1	5.28	2646

Supplementary Fig 10. RNA expression tables displaying mean UMIs in 10 subclasses of human dopamine neuron clusters from the Kamath et. al 2022 dataset.

Supplementary Note 12. *VAV2* and *DAT* transporter trafficking in the mesolimbic pathway

The literature supports that LAR-family RPTPs dephosphorylate tyrosine residues involved in *RET* activation, as well as prevent dimerization to ultimately hinder autophosphorylation. These interactions are independent of glial cell-line derived neurotrophic factor (*GDNF*), *RET*'s canonical ligand, and serve to downregulate *RET* signaling pathways (Uetani et al., 2009; Qiao et al., 2001). The loss of *PTPRD* may result in hyperactivated *RET* signaling. *GDNF* stimulation induces Tyr-905 phosphorylation of *RET*, which is accompanied by a rise in *VAV2* tyrosine phosphorylation (Zhu et al. 2015). Interestingly, *VAV2* is an essential mediator of *DAT* transporter membrane trafficking for DA neurons in the ventral tegmental area (Zhu et al. 2015). *VAV2* gene knockdown mice experienced increased levels of surface *DAT*,

leading to significantly increased concentrations of intracellular DA in the nucleus accumbens. Consequently, the mutants exhibited lower cocaine-induced locomotor activation, a behavioral response highly correlated with the capacity to rapidly upregulate *DAT* upon cocaine administration (Mandt & Zahniser, 2011). When compared to the WT, *VAV2*-deficient mice exhibited elevated surface *DAT* in the nucleus accumbens after saline solution exposure, and exhibited decreased surface *DAT* after cocaine administration. The researchers did not experiment with *VAV2* overexpressive mice, however surface *DAT* was measured in culture with plasmid transfections of *VAV2* and constitutively activated *VAV2* HEK293 cells engineered to stably overexpress *DAT*. Western blots displayed significantly less surface *DAT* in the *VAV2* over-expressive and constitutively activated *VAV2* HEK293 cultures (Zhu et al. 2015). These findings are suggestive of *VAV2*'s role in the bidirectional trafficking of *DAT*. *TrkB* hyperexcitability and consequent increases in *RET* and *VAV2* tyrosine phosphorylation in the absence of *PTPRD* may result in increased *VAV2/RET* mediated endocytosis of *DAT*, which may underlie the observed behavioral responses to cocaine in *PTPRD* KO/inhibition mice.

Expression summary for gene: RET

Cell_Type	Mean	N Cells
CALB1_CALCR	5.73	2479
CALB1_CRYM_CCDC68	4.76	931
CALB1_GEM	5.24	884
CALB1_PPP1R17	2.44	1358
CALB1_RBP4	5.69	763
CALB1_TRHR	4.76	486
Other	0.19	412292
SOX6_AGTR1	4.70	8498
SOX6_DDT	5.51	2414
SOX6_GFRA2	5.41	1589
SOX6_PART1	5.25	2646

Supplementary Fig 11. RNA expression tables displaying mean UMIs in 10 subclasses of human dopamine neuron clusters from the Kamath et. al 2022 dataset.

Supplementary Note 13. *ERK1/2* and *DAT* transporter

ERK1/2 regulates dopamine transporter surface expression and transport capacity (Moron et al. 2003). The inactivation of *ERK1/2* in DA neurons results in an increase of surface *DAT* transporter and a reduction in *DAT* phosphorylation, leading to decreased DA under the curve (Bernstein et al. 2024). Mice that received a Cre-dependent AAV to overexpress mitogen-activated protein kinase 3 and inhibit *ERK1/2* signaling in VTA dopaminergic neurons exhibited significant reduction in motivation for cocaine with less breakpoints and lever presses than the wildtype. However, *ERK1/2* inactivation did not alter cocaine self-administration and rate of cocaine intake (Bernstein et al. 2024). In the context of *PTPRD* KO/inhibition, it is important to note that the literature is mixed in supporting elevated phosphorylation of *ERK1/2*. Conditional knockouts of *PTPRD* in *EMX1*+ neural progenitor cells only increased phosphorylation of *MEK1/2* in mice, whereas global mice knockouts of *PTPRD* increased both phosphorylation of *MEK1/2* and *ERK1/2* (Cortés et al., 2024). Further research would be necessary to verify if *PTPRD* inhibition in DA neurons results in altered *ERK1/2* activity. However, it is plausible that *PTPRD* inhibition in DA neurons hyperactivates *ERK1/2* signaling, resulting in chronic excitability from excessive deactivation of *KCNQ2* ion channels and aberrant homeostatic control of *ERK1/2*-mediated surface *DAT* expression and phosphorylation.

Supplementary Note 14. *PKC* signaling and *DAT*

The literature is consistent in supporting protein kinase C (*PKC*) as a downstream effector of *BDNF* signaling (Lanuza et al. 2019). Interestingly, *PKC* is heavily implicated in *DAT* transporter trafficking (Gabriel et al. 2013). Sustained activation of *PKC*, typically by phorbol

esters, drives rapid, clathrin and dynamin-dependent internalization of *DAT* into endosomes and lysosomes, lowering surface *DAT* and DA uptake capacity (Daniels et al. 1999) (Sorkina et al. 2005). *PKC* inhibitors block this phorbol ester–induced *DAT* loss (Daniels et al. 1999). *PKC* encompasses bidirectional *DAT* transporter trafficking regulation, a very brief (≤ 90 s) amphetamine administration selectively recruits *PKC β* to drive rapid *DAT* exocytosis to the plasma membrane, boosting surface *DAT* and amphetamine-stimulated DA efflux from the synapse (Chen et al. 2008) (Johnson et al. 2005b). During prolonged amphetamine exposure (60 min), WT synaptosomes revert to *DAT* internalization, whereas *PKC β* -deficient mice show delayed *DAT* insertion at 60 min, demonstrating that *PKC β* is involved in both the timing and directionality of *DAT* trafficking (Chen et al. 2008). The absence of *PTPRD* may result in hyperactivation of *PKC* signaling, attenuating the ability of DA neurons to maintain homeostatic control of *DAT* surface levels.

Expression summary for gene: PRKCB

Cell_Type	Mean	N Cells
CALB1_CALCR	12.26	2479
CALB1_CRYM_CCDC68	8.33	931
CALB1_GEM	11.43	884
CALB1_PPP1R17	5.18	1358
CALB1_RBP4	7.40	763
CALB1_TRHR	13.08	486
Other	3.48	412292
SOX6_AGTR1	10.51	8498
SOX6_DDT	6.63	2414
SOX6_GFRA2	6.93	1589
SOX6_PART1	7.13	2646

Supplementary Fig 12. RNA expression tables displaying mean UMIs in 10 subclasses of human dopamine neuron clusters from the Kamath et. al 2022 dataset.

Supplementary Note 15. *PTPRD*-F1 model proposal

Collectively, the literature combined with *PTPRD*'s significance for F1 in the DA neuron H-MAGMA analysis suggest that *PTPRD* indirectly regulates dopaminergic neuroplasticity. In the DA neuron H-MAGMA analysis, of the statistically significant GWAS SNPs mapped to *PTPRD* ($p < 5e-08$), all were either intronic or intergenic. No missense, frameshift, or nonsense mutation SNPs passed significance thresholds, suggesting that the differential expression of *PTPRD* contributes to the development of ADHD, MDD, and BPD as opposed to changes in amino acid sequence. Loss of *PTPRD*'s D1 phosphatase domain may permit the hyperactivation of *TrkB* and *RET* signaling pathways, resulting in chronic excitation and aberrant, DAT-mediated uptake of synaptic dopamine. Hyperactivated *TrkB* and *RET* signaling may increase *ERK1/2*, *PKC*, and *VAV2* phosphorylation and activity. The elevated occurrence of downstream *VAV2* mediated dendritic spine head growth likely attenuates homeostatic control of structural LTP that respond to glutamatergic input. The elevated downstream occurrence of phosphorylated *ERK1/2* may attenuate homeostatic control of both *DAT* transporter surface expression and *KCNQ2* K⁺ ion channels. The elevated occurrence of downstream *PKC* and *VAV2* activation may attenuate homeostatic control of bidirectional *DAT* transporter surface expression. In addition, excessive *TrkB* signaling may induce elevated retrograde inhibition of inhibitory GABAergic synapses (Inhibitory LTP). The coalescence of these *PTPRD* risk factors may lead to the chronic excitation of DA neurons through increases of structural and inhibitory LTP and decreased *DAT*-mediated synaptic dopamine uptake, from which the D1 and D2 receptors become desensitized. These factors may alter neuroplasticity and metaplasticity in DA neurons, increasing the signaling threshold to induce optimal potentiation of both structural and inhibitory LTP and DA-mediated signal transduction between dopaminergic neurons to maintain reward-associated circuit

homeostasis. We propose that these mechanisms underlie the consistent trend of altered behavioral responses to cocaine in *PTPRD*-deficient mice, especially in regards to decreased motivation for cocaine.

Supplementary Note 16. Exploratory, hypothesis-generating *PTPRD* fine-mapping using 1000 Genomes external reference panel and F1 summary statistics

The H-MAGMA DA neuron variant annotation mapped SNPs to *PTPRD* from 7.4 Mb to 12 Mb on chromosome 9, suggestive of cis-regulatory elements (We will refer to this region as *PTPRD* extended). In attempts to explore the gene's histology and encompass any potential regulatory features, we used the same bounds to extend our lens of *PTPRD* past its hg19 standardized coordinates on chromosome 9, 8314246-10612723. We then estimated causal SNP posterior inclusion probabilities and local heritability for F1 in regions of interest, as well as analyzed the LD structure of *PTPRD* extended (Supplementary Fig 13). As seen in Fig..., there is a significant downstream spike in LD from about 10.9Mb to 12Mb on chromosome 9. Functionally relevant domains such as expression quantitative trait loci (eQTLs), methylation quantitative trait loci (meQTLs), and chromatin loops exhibit reduced recombination (Liu et al., 2017). This region may host a plethora of regulatory elements. However, it is important to note that the use of external reference panels with small sample size that lack in-sample genotypes, such as the 1000 Genomes Project we utilize, introduce bias and unstable estimates. We acknowledge that LD estimates and causal posterior inclusion probabilities may be noisy; results should therefore be interpreted with caution.

PTPRD Extended LD (r^2) - Chr 9: 7.4Mb to 12Mb

Supplementary Fig 13. Linkage disequilibrium heatmap of *PTPRD* extended (Chr 9: 7.4Mb to 12Mb), consisting of the top off-diagonals of an r^2 matrix calculated using the 1000 Genomes Project EUR reference panel. The blue box highlights the aforementioned recombination valley (Chr 9, 10.9Mb to 12 Mb).

Concurrently, there is an F1 risk locus within this elevated region of LD just a few hundred kilobases downstream of the hg19 standardized *PTPRD* coordinates. This locus encompasses 574 F1 significant SNPs ($p < 5e-08$), and 3 F1 index SNPs ($r^2 < 0.1$ and $p < 5e-08$). Using LAVA, we estimated local genetic heritability using the F1 summary statistics as input (Werme et. al 2022). The observed local SNP heritability for the elevated region of LD from 10.9Mb to 12Mb on chromosome 9 was $1.17e-04$ ($p\text{-value} = 9.29e-07$), and for *PTPRD* extended the observed local SNP heritability was $5.66e-04$ ($p\text{-value} = 4.2e-35$). The estimates suggest that these regions harbor significant F1 SNP heritability, magnitudes more than would what would be expected by chance. To define a risk locus for further analysis in the context of *PTPRD* fine-mapping, we added 100 Kb to both the most upstream F1 index SNP and to the most

downstream SNP mapped to *PTPRD* from the midbrain dopaminergic H-MAGMA annotation in attempts to encapsulate a larger percentage of the F1 risk locus's regulatory features (Fig 19). We then utilized mixer-finemap to estimate causal posterior inclusion probabilities for each SNP in the risk locus (Akdeniz et al. 2024). Given the concurrence of abnormally high SNP heritability and reduced recombination, this region may be a DA neuron regulatory domain, housing cis-eQTLs for *PTPRD* and a plethora of other genes.

Supplementary Fig 14. F1 Manhattan plot of *PTPRD* extended with the *PTPRD* risk locus bounds denoted by the red dotted lines and standardized hg19 *PTPRD* coordinates denoted by the green dotted lines.

PTPRD Extended LD (r^2) - Chr 9: 7.4Mb to 12Mb

Supplementary Fig 15. Linkage disequilibrium heatmap of *PTPRD* extended with the *PTPRD* risk locus highlighted by the green dotted line (Chr 9, 10968693 to 1170987), consisting of the top off-diagonals of an r^2 matrix calculated using the 1000 Genomes Project EUR reference panel

PTPRD Risk Locus LD (r^2) - Chr 9: 10968693 to 11709873

Supplementary Fig 16. Linkage disequilibrium heatmap of PTPRD risk locus), consisting of the top off-diagonals of an r^2 matrix calculated using the 1000 Genomes Project EUR reference panel

SNP	BP	PIP	EffectSize	Variance
rs141210519	11,223,536	0.990	-0.001330	0.00404
rs62527890	11,040,767	0.979	-0.001050	0.00372
rs80040041	11,694,950	0.959	0.000598	0.00369
rs17794181	11,547,835	0.943	0.000492	0.00364
rs76671825	11,584,217	0.942	0.000491	0.00364
rs78754091	11,012,612	0.938	-0.000369	0.00365
rs117847840	11,026,766	0.930	-0.000330	0.00361
rs7038937	11,596,751	0.929	0.000422	0.00357
rs1822391	11,626,303	0.928	0.000422	0.00357
rs192356171	11,214,418	0.928	-0.000215	0.00364
rs117321073	11,058,568	0.922	-0.000304	0.00359
rs117715585	11,601,119	0.906	0.000332	0.00352
rs142313641	11,705,797	0.905	0.000370	0.00350
rs10124075	11,519,178	0.889	0.000321	0.00346
rs2821161	11,655,676	0.889	0.000320	0.00346
rs2821158	11,664,363	0.889	0.000320	0.00346
rs2586362	11,652,617	0.888	0.000320	0.00346
rs13288265	11,269,531	0.884	-0.000794	0.00333
rs78416586	11,521,115	0.884	0.000318	0.00347
rs79330488	11,611,966	0.883	0.000317	0.00347
rs147832688	11,534,139	0.883	0.000317	0.00347
rs117251562	11,691,436	0.861	-0.000154	0.00345
rs145128084	11,014,060	0.859	0.000185	0.00344
rs13284630	11,580,191	0.855	-0.000663	0.00331
rs146472183	11,101,636	0.846	-0.000183	0.00342
rs79540937	11,101,748	0.828	-0.000163	0.00338
rs13299603	11,491,105	0.816	-0.000550	0.00328
rs189617866	11,691,641	0.810	-0.000150	0.00335
rs117474039	11,409,578	0.809	-0.000113	0.00335
rs72696288	11,331,681	0.785	-0.000660	0.00314

Supplementary Fig 17. Top 30 SNPs from mixer-finemapping analysis of the *PTPRD* risk locus (Chr 9, 10968693 to 11709873), with posterior inclusion probabilities, effect sizes, and variance.